

SALTO

Landing Legs: A MT-Aerospace composite application for Reusable Launcher

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MT-Aerospace Heritage in CFRP

MT Aerospace can map the entire value chain of all necessary process steps, ranging from design layout, topology optimisation, process development, material selection, manufacturing, integration, non-destructive testing (NDI) functional testing and qualification/certification.

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Structures & Structural Tanks

- Sandwich technologies for satellite, aircrafts, helicopter
- Surface treatment with carbon fibre reinforced thermoplastics
- Demonstrator of composite cryogenic tank

CFRP Booster

- Design, manufacture and test of CFRP solid rocket motor case demonstrator
- Technology maturation of dry fibre application and resin infusion
- Thermoplastic materials for highly loaded structures in the aerospace field

Pressure Vessels

- Hydraulic/pneumatic high pressure vessel
- Leading supply of satellite tanks (PMD tanks, Diaphragm tanks, Bladder tanks, High-pressure vessels)
- Development and manufacturing of water tanks for aircrafts
- Design, manufacturing and test of high pressure vessel for storage of hydrogen and other fluids in a wide range of temperatures from cryogenic conditions up to an elevated ambient temperature.
- Technology development for a CFRP upper stage LOX and LH2 Tank

Objectives of Landing leg development

In frame of SALTO, MT-Aerospace is in charge of the concept development of integrated structure design for landing legs and the manufacture a Themis T3 landing leg demonstrator.

Demonstrator description

The designed and manufactured Landing legs demonstrator has a leg length of 5,9m, a width of 2,3m and weight of approx. 500 kg. For efficient purpose, composite material was selected as lightweight solution.

General information

Within this context, MT-Aerospace is contracted within SALTO to develop a landing leg system. The Themis programme is an ongoing European Space Agency (ESA) programme that is developing a prototype reusable rocket.

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Within this work package, previous gained MT-Aerospace knowledge from the project RETALT (Retro Propulsion Assisted Landing) is transferred to a full-scale demonstrator, which was designed/justified/manufactured and finally tested.

- Shock Absorber Assembly (SAAY primary strut): A telescopic strut including a locking mechanism, a damper system, transferring load from deployment and landing to the core stage
- Landing Leg Assembly (LLAY secondary strut): Aerodynamic cover protecting the Landing leg from thermal load and transferring load from deployment and landing to the core stage

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Analysis of data from RETALT and TIH

To reach the first goal, a requirements screening based on RETALT experience was done. The RETALT project, funded by the European Horizon 2020 program, has the objective to study critical technologies for Vertical Take-off Vertical Landing (VTVL) Reusable Launch Vehicles (RLVs) applying retro propulsion, combined with aerodynamic control surfaces and landing gear components.

The following main requirements of RETALT were analysed:

- **Functionality:** Definition of locking and unlocking mechanism, deployment system
- **Interface:** Interface to launcher, aerodynamic optimized structure
- **Environment:** Definition of thermal and vibrating environment
- **Loading/Physics:** Derivation of QSL loading based on MT-Aerospace assumptions

Functionality

The functionality requirement of the landing legs is including:

- Deployment passively under gravity w.o. external systems
- Mechanical locking system
- Unlocking of the mechanical mechanism after latching w.o. dismantling the total landing leg
- Sustaining the deployment and landing loads w.o. impact of the function of the landing leg by a hydraulic damper and crushable elements to avoid over loading
- No refurbishment foreseen for the landing leg except the TPS system

Manufacturing

The manufacturing of the demonstrator is based on AFP process with lay-up and autoclave applications.

Composite parts are prepared with 3D printed tooling which provide the surface for lay-up application. The main advantages of this process are the very low delivery time and reduced cost compared to a state-of-the-art CFRP tooling.

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Full scale assembly deployment test

The scope of the full-scale assembly deployment test is to perform a specified drop test of a landing gear as planned and extract important data out of the test to improve the general understanding of the structural behaviour of a landing gear during landing.

The general purpose of this activity is:

- to provide a proof of concept of the selected design solution for energy absorption representative of deployment conditions before landing
- validation of structural behaviour as expected (deformation strains etc.) under high dynamic shock loading

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Conclusion

All the goals defined in grant agreement were successfully demonstrated by MT-Aerospace. During the development and manufacturing of the landing leg a lot of information about loads, kinematics and manufacturing processes was collected. The TR-level reached 3-4, depending on different aspects such as landing, deployment, environmental conditions.

For the future development, respectively flight hardware, the following steps are required:

- Detailed technical specification including all requirements on system level
- Elaboration of system overview including all electrical and mechanical elements
- Local adaption of MT-Aerospace's design towards strength depending on TRS load definition
- Definition of test campaign to qualify hardware

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